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Zine template Matthew Gravelyn <https://mr-matthew.itch.io/half-page-booklet>

Original call for contributors <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15208123>

View this zine online <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16938657>

Print your own copy <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16938846>

Fat people experience substantial marginalization, due in large part to scientific rationalization. In opposition, fat liberation is a social movement aimed at dismantling anti-fatness: a form of discrimination which has been explored by fat studies scholars in other fields, but has received limited attention from science and technology studies (STS) researchers.

In response to this, we invited contributions from STS scholars, Society for Social Studies of Science (4S) community members, and researchers and activists interested in advancing fat liberation in science and technology to contribute to

FAT STS

a zine

When bigger is better

FATTENING STS

In a world that wants me to be smaller, when is bigger better?

SOME EXAMPLES:

- When a body is used to hold a cup of tea!
- When being bigger keeps you warm in the cold, is protective and comforting
- When facing serious medical concerns that stop ingestion, sap energy and body resources
- When bigger is your body's default and contorting yourself into societies ideal can have serious harmful side effects such as eating disorders, wasted energy, and potential
- When being bigger challenges weight stigma in healthcare that withholds proper medical treatment from people in larger bodies
- When being small limits your focus to food and reduces joy

WHEN IT FREES PEOPLE FROM
COERCION, EXPLOITATION, CONTROL
AND GUILT

STS scholars examine how cultural values shape what is considered legitimate knowledge. Acknowledging that bigger bodies can be better would support the unpicking of the social stigma against fatness as a scientific force that influences how research questions are framed, which studies get funded, and how results are interpreted.

In doing so, fat STS critiques how scientific "truths" about fatness are entangled with moral, racial, gendered, and economic judgments.

Fat STS: Encouraging Joy

more
to
read

QZAP - The Queer Zine Archive Project - Archiving Queer zines since 2003. *Queer Zine Archive Project*. <https://gittings.qzap.org/>

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disabled

QUEER

JOY!

t. miller * @talyaelaine

WHY BMI? $\frac{\text{Weight (kg)}}{[\text{Height(m)}]^2}$

Adolphe Quetelet (1796-1874) tried to define 'the average man.'

Porter, T.M. (1985) 'The Mathematics of Society: Variation and Error in Quetelet's Statistics', *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 18(1), pp. 51-69.

In 1972, his 'Quetelet index' was found to be a 'slightly better' correlation for fatness than other measures (for men). It was renamed the 'body mass index.'

SUMMARY

Analyses are reported on the correlation with height and with subcutaneous fat thickness of relative weight expressed as per cent of average weight at given height, and of the ratios weight/height, weight/height squared, and the ponderal index (cube root of weight divided by height) in 7424 'healthy' men in 12 cohorts in five countries. Analyses are also reported on the relationship of those indicators of relative weight to body density in 180 young men and in 248 men aged 49-59.

Judged by the criteria of correlation with height (lowest is best) and to measures of body fatness (highest is best), the ponderal index is the poorest of the relative weight indices studied. The ratio of weight to height squared, here termed the body mass index, is slightly better in these respects than the simple ratio of weight to height. The body mass index seems preferable over other indices of relative weight on these grounds as well as on the simplicity of the calculation and, in contrast to percentage of average weight, the applicability to all populations at all times.

Keys, A. et al. (1972) 'Indices of relative weight and obesity', *Journal of Chronic Diseases*, 25(6-7), pp. 329-343. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9681\(72\)90027-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9681(72)90027-6).

In 1998, the World Health Organisation used the BMI to classify people into 'underweight', 'normal', 'overweight' and 'obese' categories.

Table 2.1 Classification of overweight in adults according to BMI

Classification	BMI (kg/m ²)	Risk of co-morbidities
Underweight	< 18.5	Low (but risk of other clinical problems increased)
Normal range	18.5-24.9	Average
Overweight	≥ 25	
Pre-obese	25-29.9	Increased
Obese class I	30.0-34.9	Moderate
Obese class II	35.0-39.9	Severe
Obese class III	≥ 40.0	Very severe

World Health Organization (1998) *Obesity: Preventing and Managing the Global Epidemic*. Available at: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/63884>.

NHS Health A to Z | NHS services | Live Well | Mental health | Care and support

Home > Health assessment tools

Calculate your body mass index (BMI)

Check an adult's or child's BMI to find out if they're a healthy weight. It's important to use the right calculator for adults (aged 18 and over) or children and teenagers (aged between 2 and 17).

Now my doctor uses the BMI to decide if my weight is 'healthy' enough to get healthcare.

Cadet Ozempic and the War on Obesity

Nikkola Brown

UNC Greensboro, MA in English

Recently, a family friend was diagnosed with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. We encouraged her to talk to her doctor about Rezdiffra, the first medicine approved by the FDA to treat NASH alongside diet and exercise (Rezdiffra). Her doctor's response was to put her on Ozempic for weight loss.

She's not fat.

We're no stranger to liver disease or obesity in my family. All of us have gone through every weight loss program with little success. Most of my family is fat and have NASH. Though I have no signs of liver disease yet, I expect it will one day find me.

Obesity has become a scapegoat for most metabolic diseases. Though there is a visible scientific connection between the two, fatness has become the global punching bag of constant cause. This practice dismisses the causes of obesity: genetics, stress, the neoliberal lack of time for healthy exercise and cooking, the cost of healthy, non-processed

groceries, and environmental hazards. Obesity becomes a "you" problem, rather than a systemic one.

Our friend is not fat. She's not like me, with my BMI so high, doctors glare at me for asking for help. She's not like my mom or my aunt or my dad or my cousins or any of the people I'm related to. By all means, losing weight is not going to magically control her NASH. GLP-1s, though a useful tool for people ready to lose weight on their own terms, are becoming an additional technology to enforce scientific bias against obesity.

In the short story "The Pill," Meg Elison describes a magical cure for obesity, a pill that causes all excess fat and skin to disappear in three days. The process is risky, with one in ten people who take the Pill dying as their heart gives out from the process (Elison). Despite the risk, the FDA in Elison's America approves the drug. The Pill is an overnight success with widespread acceptance (Elison). More concerning is how

"The laws changed that year, but they wouldn't go into effect until January. They weren't making it illegal to be fat,

exactly. But it was as close as they could get. It was going to be legal to deny health insurance to anyone with a BMI over 25 if they refused the Pill. Intentional obesity would also be grounds for loss of child custody, and would be acceptable reason for dismissal from a job." (Elison)

I recount this story not to fear-monger. At this time, no insurance is denying a person coverage for being fat, but I don't put it past insurance companies. American medical care is a free market where every person's health is for sale. On Aflac's website, they explain that Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes can qualify for life insurance policies. However, "[their] premiums may be higher since insurers consider [their] personal and family health history when calculating premiums" (Aflac). I've watched my parents fill out their open enrollment forms and be denied coverage because of their diabetes, my mom's cancer, and now her transplant. For me, Elison's insurance companies and the legalized hatred of fat people bear an eerie similarity.

I say this not to prevent the use of the use of GLP-1s, but instead encourage rhetorical

caution. Systematically, fat people are at a disadvantage. I know fat bodies, especially for people of color, face these systemic barriers even more. GLP-1s are a powerful technology that have the power to help so many; however, as cases such as our family friend show, they run the risk of stigmatizing and legitimizing fat hatred in the medical system. I suggest that instead of using them as a blanket solution, we encourage open dialogue and embrace talk about what it really means to use them.

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- Print at full size (instead of 'to fit' the pages);
- Print pages 1-8;
- Print 2 pages per sheet (without adding margins);
- Print on both sides of US letter size paper (8.5 x 11 inches);
- Flip on the short edge of the paper.

Fold your stack of papers in half.

Staple in the middle (if you want to).